

DELAMINATION CHARACTERIZATION OF A UNIDIRECTIONAL LAMINATE
WITH INSIDE PLYS CUT

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1. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The eight-ply unidirectional symmetrical laminate with an average thickness of 1.08mm and an average fiber-volume content of 60% was fabricated from 914C/TS-5 graphite/epoxy prepregs. The stacking sequence of the laminate is $0_2, \theta_2 S$. The θ_2 here stands for two layers whose fibers were cut. The defects were introduced by cutting prepregs at stacking. All the specimens were cut from $400 \times 400 \text{mm}^2$ plates and were bonded with glass-fiber reinforced plastics tabs. The specimen geometry is illustrated in Figure 1.

The load-controlled tension-tension fatigue tests ($R = 0.1$, $\sigma_m = 275, 325$ and 375 N/mm^2 , $f = 5 \text{ Hz}$) were run on specimens in a SCHENCK servo-hydraulic testing machine under the control of a microcomputer. The maximum elongation of specimens was recorded on a X-t plotter. After a prescribed cycle number, the specimen was taken out of the testing machine and sent to ultrasonic C-scan examination. Then the test continued. The same steps were repeated several times until the delaminations in specimens grew over half of strain-gauge transducer measurement length (170mm).

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2.1 Stiffness degradation

Figure 2 shows the stiffness change of laminates with the delamination growth for 8 specimens in this study. It can be understood from this diagram that the stiffness loss is approximately linearly related to the delamination length and the stress levels have no effects on this linearity. The results in our investigation are in concordance with the others' 1-3. This behavior suggests that delaminations are the main cause of stiffness loss.

Considering the above facts, a linear equation has been supposed to express the relationship between stiffness and delamination size of laminates,

$$E = E_0(1 - D) \quad (1)$$

where E = stiffness of a laminate with delamination,
 E_0 = initiation stiffness of the laminate.

In our investigation, D is defined as

$$D = c/2L \quad (2)$$

in which c is the delamination length and L is the specimen length. Taking into account

Equations 1 and 2 leads to a conclusion that the maximum stiffness loss of laminates due to delaminations is 50%.

According to the change of stiffness with fatigue cycles for 8 specimens under consideration at three stress levels, we know that the stiffness of laminates degraded roughly linearly during fatigue loading. So it can be inferred that the delaminations mainly contributed to the stiffness loss of laminates. For a given stress level, a linear function can be suggested to illustrate the stiffness change of laminates with cycling, i.e.

$$E=AN+B \quad (3)$$

where E =stiffness of a laminate with damage,
 N =number of fatigue cycle.

Commonly B can be considered as initiation stiffness of laminates. A is the stiffness loss when fatigue goes a cycle and it indicates the rate of stiffness reduction of a fatigue-loaded laminate.

2.2 Delamination growth

It is visible from C-scan pictures that cutting fibers in the middle of specimens created a favourable condition for specimens delaminations of which grew predominately in the fiber direction or loading direction. So we got a fracture process which consists mainly of Mode II fracture.

Under fatigue cycling, the damage initiated at the cutting area of central plies in the way of a few isolated cracks. After some cycles, these cracks joined each other and the delaminations began. Then, with the continuing of the test, delaminations developed nearly in a constant rate and symmetrically at the interfaces of 2nd/3rd and 6th/7th plies. There are a few matrix cracks in longitudinal direction. But these matrix cracks remained small through the whole test compared to delaminations. Therefore their effects on the stiffness are negligible.

The delamination growth rate dc/dN is available if equations 1 and 2 are combined and differentiated. A power law has been applied to describe the relationship between dc/dN and stress intensity factor, i.e.

$$dc/dN = \alpha \Delta K^\beta \quad (4)$$

where α and β are constants that need to be determined experimentally and ΔK is the stress intensity factor range which can be calculated as follows

$$\Delta K = (1-R) \sqrt{G/R^{22}} \quad (5)$$

in which R is stress ratio and R^{22} is a material constant. A formula for strain energy release rate G has been derived in the way of strength-of-materials,

$$G = P^2 / 2WF_L E_L \quad (6)$$

where P =external load,
 W =width of a laminate,
 F_L =cross section of the laminate, and
 E_L =modulus of a laminate without damage.

It is obvious from Equation 6 that G related to the delamination growth is influenced only by external load when materials of which laminates are made are given. Figure 3 shows the change of dc/dN with ΔK in a double logarithmic X-Y coordinate system.

3. CONCLUSIONS

1. A linear equation can be used to express the change of the laminate stiffness with the delamination growth.
2. The delamination growth is a stable fracture process. Transverse cracks initiate at the cutting and delaminations grow symmetrically at the interfaces of cut and uncut layers. The stress amplitude has significant effects on the delamination growth rate. This behavior can be described in a power law.
3. It has been shown by the method of strength-of-materials that through the whole fatigue cycling the strain energy release rate corresponding to the delamination is a constant which is only related to stress levels.

4. Figures

Figure 1. Specimen geometry

Figure 2. Change of stiffness with delamination growth

Figure 3. Change of stiffness with cycling. spec. 196/7 and 197/1